

EVOLUTION OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL CONTENT

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the evolution of digital content used in education. The study examines the role of digital technologies, online learning platforms and interactive tools in the learning process, as well as compares them with traditional teaching methods. The article is devoted to the historical formation of digital content, as well as its theoretical and practical foundations, innovative approaches and prospects. The study analyzes the effectiveness of the digitalization of the education system and the impact of new technological solutions on students, teachers and the entire educational process.*

Keywords: *content, content types, education, ICT, digital technologies, electronic textbooks, educational evolution.*

INTRODUCTION. The rapid development of digital technologies over the past decade has led to revolutionary changes in the field of education. The Internet, mobile devices and interactive platforms have made it possible to move the educational process from traditional methods to digital. This process has led not only to the digitization of educational materials, but also to a fundamental change in teaching methods.

The following is an analysis of the emergence, development, and integration of digital content into the education system. First, a brief overview of the concept of digital content, its historical roots, and development trends is provided. This is followed by a detailed discussion of the role, advantages, and limitations of new technological solutions, interactive platforms, and virtual learning environments in the educational process.

The aim of this work is to determine the effectiveness of the digital revolution in the education system and identify possible future directions in the field of education. Based on the research results, innovative approaches and technological changes, it is also discussed what strategies can be developed to enter a new era of education.

Today we live in the age of information technology, and this creates many conveniences for us in the process of teaching or learning. Thanks to digital technologies and educational content, we now have the opportunity to learn online, discover new areas of knowledge, and develop ourselves more effectively. At this point, let's dwell on the concept of digital content for education.

Digital educational content – is a set of electronic and interactive materials used in the learning process. It is used in online learning, traditional education, and hybrid learning systems and allows students to learn more effectively [1].

For example, the crisis caused by the spread of the coronavirus COVID-19 – has been a serious test for education systems around the world. Prolonged closures of educational institutions can not only negatively affect short-term learning outcomes, but also, in the long term, lead to a decline in the quality of human capital, a decrease in student competitiveness, and a negative impact on the country's economy.

To prevent such processes and as advanced innovative solutions, distance learning and online learning technologies have developed following the development of digital technologies and Internet technologies. Digital technologies, in turn, have become the basis for the development of digital pedagogy in the educational process. The main goal of digital pedagogy is to support the educational process through technological capabilities, which is implemented using information and communication technologies (ICT). This process has been manifested partly in an increase in the quality of education, and partly in the emergence of new interactive forms of the educational process.

Such a scientific and technological revolution shaped a new reality and led to the emergence of the following concepts:

- Digital economy,
- Digital learning environment,
- Digital pedagogy,
- Digital medicine, etc.

These technological changes are making the educational process more flexible, efficient, and accessible to a wider audience [2].

It should be noted that in the digital world, in the context of changes taking place in any field, the education sector is no exception. It is difficult to imagine today's modern education system without information technologies. Because the entire education system, from managing it to teaching and learning processes, is becoming digital.

METHODOLOGY. This study examines the formation, development, and integration of digital educational content into the educational process using a historical-evolutionary approach. The following methodological approaches were used in writing the article:

1. Historical-analytical method
2. Analysis of the presented statistical and scientific sources
3. Comparison method
4. Theoretical generalization
5. Evolutionary approach

The study used scientific articles, statistical data, historical sources, international experience in the field of education, and open digital resources as the main basis. It also analyzed the changes in the modern educational environment from a practical perspective, and it was noted that the results of the article could be useful in developing digital education strategies in the future.

RESULTS. Today, we often come across the term digital content in various fields. The concept of content is becoming increasingly popular in marketing, advertising, medicine, business, economics, education, and many other fields. So what is content? What is its purpose? We will clarify these questions below.

Content– a medium of information that must be expressed through some medium, such as speech, writing, or various forms of art, for self-expression, distribution, marketing, or publication [3].

Content is created for different purposes, audiences, and platforms. We can divide it into the following main types:

- ✓ **Text content:** Blog posts, articles, website content.
- ✓ **Visual content:** Pictures, graphs, infographics.

- ✓ **Video contents:** Videos for webinars, live broadcasts, YouTube, and other similar platforms.
- ✓ **Audio contents:** Podcasts, audiobooks, and music.
- ✓ **Interactive content:** Online tests, quizzes, animations, and interactive infographics.
- ✓ **Social media content:** Posts, stories, advertising and branding materials.

Each type of content has its own advantages and areas of application, and plays an important role in attracting and informing the target audience. It is also important to remember that when creating content, it is necessary to take into account the purpose, audience needs, and the specifics of the platform.

All of the above types of content can be used in the educational process. We can generally distinguish between two types of educational content. These are traditional and digital content. In the educational process, digital and traditional content play an important role in helping students acquire knowledge, develop skills, and make the learning process interactive. Below are their main aspects:

Traditional content.

- **Printed textbooks and manuals:** It is a tried and tested and a key element of the traditional education system and is widely used by teachers in classroom settings.
- **Lectures and presentations:** The teacher's verbal explanations and presentations during the lesson are an effective tool for conveying theoretical knowledge to students.
- **Laboratory work and practical training:** It plays an important role in consolidating knowledge through practice.
- **Paper tests and assignments:** Written exams, assignments, and practical exercises allow students to study independently and monitor their knowledge.

Digital content.

- **Electronic textbooks and resources:** Books, articles, and interactive materials in PDF and ePub formats allow students to access knowledge in a timely and flexible manner.
- **Online courses and video lessons:** MOOC (massive open online courses) platforms are widely used in distance education using videos and lecture notes.
- **Interactive materials:** Animations, quizzes, games, and simulations ensure active student participation and reinforce understanding.
- **Virtual labs and simulations:** Theoretical knowledge can be transformed into practical experience by simulating practical training using computer programs.
- **Mobile applications:** Through educational apps, students will have access to resources anywhere, anytime.

By using the advantages of both types of content in the right combination in the educational process, the learning process can be made more effective and interactive. One of the most ideal solutions is to integrate digital and traditional methods, depending on the needs of teachers and students.

We will examine the emergence of digital content used in the educational process today, its entry into the field of education, and the factors underlying this from a historical and evolutionary perspective.

Digital content used in education includes platforms, materials and content in various digital formats designed to make the learning process interactive, dynamic and multimedia-rich.

Unlike traditional printed textbooks and various paper-based materials, digital content provides students with modern learning tools that are convenient, scalable and environmentally friendly [4].

Below we will explore the evolution of the emergence of digital content used in education:

In the history of education, each period has had its own methods, tools, and approaches. In the era before digital technologies, computers, and the Internet, the educational process was based on more simple methods. The initial educational materials used by teachers during this period played an important role in preparing students for the subject and in forming basic concepts. In the era before digital tools, we can understand the primary educational materials as sources in the form of handwritten written materials, textbooks, visual aids, posters, and charts. These materials were intended to introduce the subject at the beginning of the lesson, explain key terms, and attract students' attention.

It is known that the book is a product of human thought and one of the oldest means of transmitting knowledge from generation to generation. The roots of the books we use today go back to the distant past. The first books and printing houses played an invaluable role in the development of science, culture and education in the history of mankind. In particular, the emergence of written sources in the educational process was the beginning of the systematic provision of knowledge to students.

Until the mid-15th century, books were painstakingly written and copied by hand, making them scarce and expensive. In 1440, the German blacksmith and inventor Johannes Gutenberg created the world's first mechanical printing press, which dramatically increased the speed of book production. As a result, literacy rates increased and new educational opportunities opened up. Johannes Gutenberg's invention played a significant role in the development of the Renaissance and the Age of Enlightenment [5].

After 500 years, or rather in 1949, the traditional books we know today began to take on the electronic form that is popular today. Initially, a mechanical book was invented by Spanish teacher Angela Ruiz Robles. Although it was not fully electronic, it was seen as a device that could replace text. This device, created by Angela Ruiz Robles, contained a moving tape or disk inside. Each tape contained text on a topic. The reader could press a certain button to go to the desired section. The device was designed to be understandable and increase children's interest in reading. The device could be used independently by the student without the help of a teacher. This was the first step in the concept of an electronic book. Throughout her career, Angela Ruiz Robles worked to facilitate the process of teaching children, to compact textbooks, and to make reading interactive. Its main idea was to combine several heavy books into one device and simplify the reading process [6].

By 1877, American inventor Thomas Edison had invented the phonograph, a machine that allowed sound to be recorded and played back. Although the early recordings were not perfect, the phonograph made a significant contribution to the development of future audio technologies. As the phonograph was the first step in sound recording technology, it laid the foundation for the development of today's audio and multimedia technologies. Therefore, the creation of this device also laid the foundation for the development of educational tools. As an example, we can cite audio books and various audio guides [7].

The emergence of new tools that would become the basis for digital technologies increased significantly in the early 20th century. For example, in 1895, the Lumière brothers patented the Cinematographe, a film projector that led to the creation of the first moving images. Their

Cinematographe device was designed to record images on film, which later led to the creation of modern film cameras. This invention was improved and served as the basis for today's digital video cameras and digital still cameras. This breakthrough in the world of technology is considered the main reason for the emergence of today's digital video content and digital images [8].

It is no secret that various technologies created during the era of mechanical machines were the ancestors and the basis for the development of modern technologies today. The early 1940s can be said to have become the starting point of the digital age. Because the creation of the first electronic computers in the early 1940s successfully laid the foundation for the computer technologies that are used today.

The first digital computer was the Colossus, a device developed by the British in 1943 that could break various codes and encrypted messages. The main purpose of this computer was to decipher encrypted messages between German leaders and generals during World War II. Two years later, in 1945, the first general-purpose computer, the ENIAC (Electronic Numerical Integrator And Computer), was introduced. ENIAC was the most powerful computing device ever created and the first programmable general-purpose electronic digital computer. These early computers evolved and paved the way for a new era of smaller and more powerful computers.

After the first electronic digital computers were created, they developed rapidly, and this continued to open up new possibilities for education. For example, the creation of a computer called PLATO at the University of Illinois in 1960 laid the foundation for the creation of the first computer-assisted instructional systems. By the mid-1970s, PLATO could be found with elements such as bright graphics, a touch screen, a speech synthesizer, messaging applications, games, and educational programs. Of course, these technologies, although they seem simple today, were a huge achievement for their time [9].

The development of computer technology has had a dramatic impact on the development of all spheres of society, ushering in the digital era of development. On the eve of the emergence of computers and the beginning of the digital era, humanity made another important discovery. In 1967, the Advanced Research Projects Agency Network (ARPANET) was created by the US Department of Defense's Advanced Research Projects Agency. ARPANET is the world's first computer network based on packet transmission technology.

The main task of ARPANET was to create a fast and efficient exchange of information between scientific research institutions and military organizations. It also aimed to test the stability of technologies and develop new network protocols that became the basis of the Internet. ARPANET was the first network to operate on the basis of packet transmission, which is one of the important technological foundations of the modern Internet. In addition, the TCP/IP protocol was developed on ARPANET, which is the main protocol of the current Internet. Although ARPANET was originally intended for military and scientific research, it soon began to be used to strengthen scientific cooperation between higher education institutions and research institutes. Today, it is true that Internet technologies have become an integral part of the educational sphere. [10].

Looking at the above information, we can see the enormous impact that each discovery and evolution has had on the field of education. We can see that the invention of various devices, from mechanical machines to the early ancestors of the digital devices that are widely used today, has laid the foundation for today's modern digital technologies.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it should be emphasized that by the 21st century, the rapid development of digital technologies has fundamentally changed the education system. Above, the historical roots, formation, stages of development and current state of digital educational content were analyzed from an evolutionary perspective. In ancient times, knowledge was transmitted from generation to generation orally, and then in manuscript form, but we can see that the popularization of printed books from the 15th century laid the foundation for the systematization of education.

It is also worth emphasizing that the introduction of digital content into the education system and its evolution can be explained by the growth of the development process of human thought. Each technological breakthrough, responding to the needs of its time, has served to make education more effective, convenient and popular. In the future, digital content based on artificial intelligence, virtual and augmented reality, generative technologies, as well as individual learning algorithms, is expected to open new opportunities in the field of education. An education system that is able to adapt to such changes will form a competitive, innovative and future-ready society.

REFERENCES

1. Цифровой контент в образовании - <https://oblakoz.ru/art/cifrovoj-kontent-v-obrazovanii>
2. К.С.Пронь, А.А.Абусупьянова, Л.Ю.Анцыфорова – История развития цифровых технологий в системе образования. Молодой исследователь Дона. №3(36) 2022.
3. Kontent yaratish - https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kontent_yaratish#cite_note-2
4. Using Digital Content in Education: Past, Present, And Future - <https://www.idreameducation.org/blog/digital-content-in-education/>
5. ThoughtCo. Biography of Johannes Gutenberg, German Inventor of the Printing Press - <https://www.thoughtco.com/johannes-gutenberg-and-the-printing-press-1991865>
6. Mujeresconciencia. Ángela Ruiz Robles (1895-1975) - <https://mujeresconciencia.com/2017/05/25/angela-ruiz-robles-1895-1975/>
7. Library of Congress. History of the Cylinder Phonograph - <https://www.loc.gov/collections/edison-company-motion-pictures-and-sound-recordings/articles-and-essays/history-of-edison-sound-recordings/history-of-the-cylinder-phonograph/>
8. The Lumière Cinématographe - https://artsandculture.google.com/story/the-lumi%C3%A8re-cin%C3%A9matographe-la-cin%C3%A9math%C3%A8que-fran%C3%A7aise/zgWBKU2_7WzRLA?hl=en
9. PLATO: How an educational computer system from the '60s shaped the future - <https://arstechnica.com/gadgets/2023/03/plato-how-an-educational-computer-system-from-the-60s-shaped-the-future/>
10. ARPANET - <https://www.techtarget.com/searchnetworking/definition/ARPANET>